

MECHANISMS OF INTERGRAINAL FAILURE DURING PLASTIC DEFORMATION

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Annotation. The article investigates fracture occurring during plastic deformation. It is noted that the fracture begins in two ways – due to the formation of wedge-shaped (V-shaped) cracks, which usually form at the intersection points of three grain boundaries and tend to grow along the boundaries perpendicular to the direction of the applied stress. Such V-shaped cracks can be observed in many pure metals as well as in engineering alloys such as nickel alloys and stainless steels.

Keywords: intergranular fracture, wedge-shaped cracks, main cracks, GB sliding (grain boundary sliding), V-shaped cracks, lattice dislocations.

Аннотация. В статье исследуется разрушение при пластической деформации. Указано, что оно начинается двумя путями – за счёт образования клинообразных

(V-образных) трещин, которые, как правило, формируются в точках пересечения трёх границ зёрен и стремятся расти вдоль границ, перпендикулярных направлению действующего напряжения. Такие V-образные трещины можно наблюдать у многих чистых металлов, а также у технических сплавов, таких как никелевые и нержавеющей стали.

Ключевые слова: Межзеренное разрушение, клиновидные трещины, магистральные трещины, ЗГП - зерно-границное проскальзывание, V - образные трещины, решеточные дислокации.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada plastik deformatsiya jarayonida yuzaga keladigan yemirilish jarayoni o'rganilgan. Unda yemirilish ikki yo'l bilan boshlanishi ko'rsatilgan: birinchisi — klinasimon (V-shaklli) yoriqlar hosil bo'lishi hisobiga. Bunday yoriqlar odatda uchta don (zarra) chegarasi kesishgan nuqtalarda paydo bo'ladi va ta'sir etuvchi kuchlanish yo'nalishiga perpendikulyar bo'lgan chegaralar bo'ylab o'sishga intiladi. Bunday V-shaklli yoriqlar ko'plab sof metallarda, shuningdek nikel qotishmalari va zanglamaydigan po'lat kabi texnik qotishmalarda ham kuzatilishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: donalararo yemirilish, klinasimon yoriqlar, magistral yoriqlar, ЗГП – don chegaralari bo'ylab sirpanish, V-shaklli yoriqlar, kristall panjara dislokatsiyalari.

Wedge-shaped V-shaped cracks, forming at triple grain boundary junctions, weaken the cross-section of the material. Cluster of lattice dislocations in front of the boundary weakens the grain's cross-section. Slip along the boundary with steps creates stress concentrations, which in turn cause localized vacancy flows. Vacancies coalesce into complexes, which, by absorbing new vacancies, grow into pores. Pores (O-shaped cracks) can be elliptical in cross-section; they gradually increase in number and size. The massive formation of pores and their influence leads to a main crack and ultimately to complete failure of the material [1,2].

Fracture initiates in at least two ways: through the formation of wedge-shaped cracks and more or less spherical pores. Wedge-shaped (V-shaped) cracks typically form at the intersections of three boundaries (Fig. 1) and tend to grow along grain boundaries normal to the direction of the applied stress (1).

This type of crack typically occurs during low-temperature plasticity and high stresses. Its occurrence is associated with grain boundary slip, which, due to stress

concentration, can lead to crack opening at the intersection of three boundaries in several ways. Such V-shaped cracks can be observed in a wide range of pure metals and in technical alloys, such as nickel (Fig. 3) or stainless steel (Fig. 2) [3, 4].

Wedge-shaped cracks, forming at triple grain boundary junctions, weaken the cross-section of the material. This accelerates the formation of new microcracks at other boundaries. The massive formation of microcracks leads to their coalescence into main cracks and ultimately to complete failure of the material (2).

Figure 1. Mechanisms of crack formation at the intersection of three boundaries

Figure 2. Primary wedge-shaped cracks in stainless steel (316N) (a) and their merging into a main crack (b).

The second pathway for grain boundary crack formation was first observed by Greenwood et al., who discovered small spherical pores at grain boundaries in a number of metals and alloys at the onset of the third stage of creep. These pores (O-shaped cracks) can be circular or elliptical in cross-section; they gradually increase in number and size during the third stage of plasticity (Fig. 2) [5, 6].

At low temperatures, observations show that the pores are typically spaced approximately $1 \mu\text{m}$ apart and have a diameter of no more than $1 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 3. Wedge-shaped cracks resulting from creep of Ti alloy (a) and the diagram of their formation (b)

There may be several causes for the formation of pores at boundaries. Clusters of lattice dislocations in front of a boundary and sliding along stepped boundaries create stress concentrations, which in turn trigger localized vacancy flows. Vacancies form complexes, which, by absorbing new vacancies, grow into pores.

Let's consider the influence of some important factors on these two types of fracture.

The influence of temperature. Since grain boundary sliding increases with increasing temperature, it is expected that the tendency for intergranular cracks to form will also increase. Moreover, at high temperatures, a transition from V-shaped cracks to O-shaped cracks occurs. With increasing temperature, the number of pores per unit boundary length also increases; this has been shown to be related to the degree of development of the grain boundary fracture [7, 8].

Some experiments have found that the distribution density of pores located along grain boundaries decreases at very high temperatures; this is the result of grain boundary migration, which thus moves away from the pores that formed previously at them.

The influence of stress. It is often difficult to separate the effects of stress and temperature, but in general, at a constant temperature, a decrease in stress favors the formation of pores to a greater extent than V-shaped cracks. The greater the stress at a given temperature, the shorter the time required for intergranular fracture—this is a general rule for the behavior of metals during plasticity. Since high stresses promote V-shaped fracture, it follows that this type of crack grows faster than fracture by pore coalescence [10, 11].

The type of stress significantly influences pore formation and the region where they arise. Experiments with bicrystals show that stresses normal to the boundary

surface do not cause pore formation, as in this case the boundary is not subjected to shear stress, and thus, slip along the boundary does not occur. On the other hand, if slip occurs along a grain boundary, the imposed tensile stress often promotes pore formation [12].

CONCLUSIONS: Pore formation during tensile creep testing occurs primarily along boundaries located at angles of 60° to 90° to the tensile axis. However, in some cases, they form at boundaries located at smaller angles, and sometimes even parallel to the tensile axis. Compressive stresses generally help reduce the number of cracks that form, but do not completely eliminate their occurrence. Under hydrostatic compression imposed on the tensile specimen, pore formation is greatly hindered.

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